

We'll have that...and that... and, oh, just everything!

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The Set-up

The Australian War Memorial in Canberra possesses a wide-ranging and significant collection of large technology objects related to the experience of Australians in conflict. As well as the more well-known objects, such as the Lancaster bomber “G for George” and the Japanese midget submarine, it includes a variety of mechanised vehicles, including tracked-laying armoured vehicles, trucks, four wheel drives, cars, motorcycles, and other specialised vehicle types.

In the late 1990s, the condition of this collection of vehicles was highly varied: some vehicles had arrived direct from the military in fully serviceable order, and had been kept that way, while others were non-functional and, in some cases, badly deteriorated. Based on the idea that operation is the best way to preserve complex mechanical systems, a maintenance program had been started in the early 1990s to maintain those already in operational condition, with the aim of bringing further vehicles up to this standard as time and money permitted. Some, such as the Centurion and T34 tanks, were kept operational principally to enable them to move under their own power. Two, a Land Rover mounting a 106mm recoilless rifle (Fig. 1), and a recovery vehicle, the M816 Wrecker, were also roadworthy and registered, and were occasionally driven to events around Canberra as mobile promotional displays.

Fig 1. The Land Rover mounting a 106mm recoilless rifle, which was sometimes driven to promotional events. Reproduced with permission from the Australian War Memorial.

As well as being in a variety of physical states, the vehicles represented different collecting approaches. In accordance with the philosophies of Charles Bean and John Treloar, the founders of the Memorial's collection, many of the vehicles had been collected for their provenance rather than their technology, their ability to tell stories of places, people and events.¹ Others, however, had been collected more for their ability to represent the technology of a period, to be illustrative "type" examples. This was an approach to collecting that developed as it became clear that, in some cases, no contemporary objects had been collected that could bear witness to important stories and events, and this had left gaps in the collection. Collecting type examples also became more necessary as significant events receded further into the past: as noted by John White, a senior curator at the Memorial, before you can tell people personal stories from a time you have to tell them about the time itself and to demonstrate the restrictions and impacts that such past technologies had on people's lives and options.²

Seeing this variety in condition, significance and value to the Memorial, the Assistant Director National Collections³ (ADNC) initiated a review of the vehicle collection. The resulting document recommended the disposal of vehicles that were found to be either inappropriate for the collection or in extremely poor condition, and the acquisition of better quality examples to fill gaps in the collection. The review also recommended that the number of vehicles that were kept in roadworthy operational condition should be increased.⁴ This led to the existing operational maintenance program being expanded into a new project. Known as the Mobile Vehicles project, the new venture was intended to increase the number of vehicles in operational condition and allow the Memorial to make better use of its vehicle collection by providing display opportunities for vehicles that would otherwise only be available to the public on rare Open Days. It was also intended to exploit a broader range of promotional event opportunities by providing event clients with a choice of vehicles that represented a wide range of periods and conflicts. This new project, with the full support of the Memorial's Director, was underway by March 2001.

¹ Michael McKernan, *Here is Their Spirit: A History of the Australian War Memorial, 1917-1990*, University of Queensland Press in association with the Australian War Memorial, Queensland, 1991, p. 207.

² John White, Senior Curator, Australian War Memorial, pers. comm., August 2010.

³ The ADNC at the time the Mobile Vehicles project was initiated was Mark Whitmore, a steam and technology enthusiast. When he took up another appointment, he was replaced by Nola Anderson, whose interests lay more towards the art and photography areas of the Memorial collection. Despite their different orientations, however, both ADNCs strove equally for the efficient management of the vehicle collection.

⁴ AWM file 01/2354, n.p. "Minute to Nola Anderson ADNC – Review of Mobile Vehicles", 24 January 2006.

A list of vehicles to be included in the project was created at this stage, with the explicit statement that the list had “been designed to represent all major conflicts in which Australia has been involved using mechanical vehicles”. It contained no less than fifteen pieces of equipment, representing eight areas of conflict (though five of these were different aspects of WW2).⁵ By the time a Mobile Historic Vehicles Policy had been drafted, predominantly to document the way the Memorial would meet the legal requirements for road use of historic vehicles, the attached list had expanded to 25 vehicles, covering 60 years worth of technological development.⁶ The list implied a lot of work: at most, two of the same model of vehicle appeared in the list, each vehicle had a unique life history that necessitated idiosyncratic maintenance and operational requirements, one vehicle was completely non-functional and two of the vehicles were yet to be acquired.

The assumptions

Within the various sections of the Memorial there was general enthusiasm about the project. Everyone who knew the vehicle collection saw a fantastic resource that was both under-developed and underutilised, and they shared the goal of making the objects fit for display in a program which furthered the Memorial’s mission of helping Australians to “remember, interpret, and understand the Australian experience of war and its enduring impact on Australian society.”⁷ With hindsight, however, it is clear that because all the participants in the project were focussed on this shared aim, the presence of secondary goals, more specific to the participants’ individual roles and backgrounds, was masked. To understand the conflicts that arose as this project progressed, it is necessary to look at what these secondary goals were, who held them, and why.

The large technology Conservation Workshop Staff⁸ were people who collectively combined many years of mechanical engineering and automotive repair experience with university level conservation training. Their engineering and automotive experience primed them to see the functional systems of the objects as a vital part of their significance – keys to why and how the objects were used – and their materials conservation orientation meant that they were also deeply concerned about the preservation of the physical material of the objects, as they saw this as evidence of the object’s history and a source of information for future research and

⁵ AWM file 01/2354, n.p. “Australian War Memorial: Vehicles for Mobile Display”, 27 March 2001.

⁶ AWM file 03/2320, n.p. “Draft Australian War Memorial Historic Vehicles Policy”, Draft Ver 2002:01.

⁷ Australian War Memorial: Annual Report 2005-2006, p. 15.

http://www.awm.gov.au/about/annual_report/ann_rep05-06.pdf. Note: in the 2005-2006 Annual Report this is referred to as an “Outcome”, but in the Corporate Plan of 2008-2011 the same text appears as the Memorial’s “Mission”.

http://www.awm.gov.au/about/AWM_Corp_Plan_08_11.pdf Web links accessed 09.09.2010.

⁸ The Workshop Staff included Andrew Schroeder, one of the authors of this paper.

display. As mentioned above, since the early 1990s the Workshop Staff had tried to implement a tiered system of inspection, exercise and repair on the vehicle collection, based on the philosophy that keeping vehicles operational was the best way to provide the regular attention, movement, lubrication and corrosion reduction that would keep their functional systems in good condition and reduce deterioration in original components. Unfortunately, limited resources had prevented the full implementation of this program on all but a few vehicles. The new Mobile Vehicles project brought high-level recognition of the need to allocate resources to the maintenance of functional systems, and seemed to offer the opportunity to extend the existing maintenance program to cover more vehicles (a view supported by the extensive list of vehicles referred to above). While the Workshop Staff were fully committed to the primary goal of the Mobile Vehicles project, which was to improve the condition of selected vehicles for mobile display, their secondary goal was to extend the maintenance program to care for a larger proportion of the Memorial's vehicle collection.

The Workshop Manager⁹ was an objects conservator who had spent many years managing large technology conservation and restoration projects. While she did not have training in mechanical engineering, her experience gave her familiarity with the logistical and managerial issues that make large technology conservation challenging; issues such as the need for regular maintenance rather than repeated restoration “binges”, the tendency for unforeseen problems to become evident only as treatment of a complex system progresses, and the need to co-ordinate sub-tasks and the provision of specialist expertise at different stages of a project. She did not see functionality as of such intrinsic importance as the Workshop staff, and her background in materials conservation made her ambivalent about the impact of maintaining functionality, as she was concerned about the potential for loss of original material and evidence as deteriorated parts were replaced or repaired. Her materials conservation background and her managerial role, however, made her value the physical evidence of history embodied in the vehicles and the detailed knowledge of the vehicles which was built up by the Workshop staff who cared for them. She saw this information as a key resource, which could only be used effectively if it was made explicit. Again, the new framework for her efforts was to organise conservation work on the vehicles to support mobile display, but her secondary goal was to document information about the vehicles, so that it could be used for better conservation and exhibition planning, and could further the Memorial's aim of being “a centre of historical research and dissemination of knowledge relating to Australian military history”.¹⁰

The Curator¹¹ of the vehicle collection was an expert in the field of military vehicles, particularly those used by Australians in conflict, and had both written on the subject

⁹ The Workshop Manager was Alison Wain, one of the authors of this paper.

¹⁰ Australian War Memorial, Corporate Plan 2005—08, p.1.

¹¹ During the period of the Mobile Vehicles project, the Curator, Mike Cecil, moved from Assistant Curator to Head of Military Heraldry and Technology. This changed

and maintained a private collection of operating military vehicles before taking up a curatorial position at the Memorial. He saw the objects principally as type examples which could be used to illustrate thematic stories of the chronology, range and importance of vehicles in military operations, and he was less interested than the Workshop Manager and Staff in the physical evidence of each vehicle's unique history. The new project provided him with the opportunity to reshape the collection by acquiring vehicles to fill thematic gaps, disposing of vehicles which were not representative of the Australian experience of war, linking related items such as gun-tractors, guns and limbers, and improving the visual qualities of the collection through repainting, and replacement of missing or damaged parts. Working in the same building as the director, he was also constantly reminded of the director's very personal enthusiasm for the project. This meant that the demands of the present were, for him, more pressing than the needs of the future. His primary goal was also to see the condition of the vehicles improved to support mobile display, but with a strong emphasis on communicating to present audiences rather than preserving information for future audiences.

The Director was formerly a Major General in the Australian Army and had trained as a mechanical engineer. Interviewed in 2009 for a study of attitudes to large technology heritage,¹² he discussed his views on the most important aspects of historic military equipment, making it clear that he found a focus on preserving the physical evidence of a particular object's history somewhat irrelevant. An example is his feelings about a hand painted message on the Beaufort bomber aircraft, which was not part of the stencilled markings that were standard for the aircraft at the time:

[The curator and conservator] put great store on [the message] "Clean your boots, clean your bloody boots" which had been painted in some black lacquer on the port side of the fuselage ... my proposition to the conservators was that is not historically interesting ...[And] it's faded post-operational service. Being [neglected] in the jungle, of course it's going to fade. Why would you need to leave it like that escapes me... it just looks incongruous and a bit twee.

What was more important to him was that an object should be fitted with the relevant standard ancillary equipment: "So it's a complete reference to that period".

The *Mark or Pattern* of the object was also important for him, because it demonstrated the ingenuity of its designers and the rigorous technical development

his involvement in the project from a close, hands-on role, to a more removed, managerial role.

¹² Steve Gower, Director of the Australian War Memorial, was interviewed by Alison Wain in 2009 for a forthcoming PhD dissertation conducted at the Australian National University.

of military equipment. Unlike the differences between individual objects, differences between successive models were not random accidents of service, but the result of a well-defined process of prototyping, approval and production, discrete steps towards increased efficiency.

... in military stuff, because you're wanting the advantage...If you've got a weakness you have got to have a make-good program to overcome the weakness. Put a mod in and off you go. Measure, counter-measure, counter-counter-measure.

The Director was, and still is, very entrepreneurial, and under his leadership the Memorial has explored many new ways to reach and develop its audience. He certainly shared the goal of improving the condition of the vehicles to support the new display, but he was ambivalent about the utility of the conservation approach and perceived it as unnecessarily expensive. He also did not trust conservators to carry out his intentions:

I think you can go too far and try and be too clever in conservation. And once you start being too clever, costs go up hyperbolically. That's why I'm always against outsourcing conservation unless you particularly carefully control it. People often talk about here in Canberra we should have the equivalent of a big Artlab for everyone. I'm not a supporter of that. I don't want to send my stuff away to be done there, because I'll just have to pay the bill and they will conserve it how they want to.

With his eye firmly on the cost benefits of the project, the Director's secondary goal was to maximise the number of vehicles that were available for operational display and minimise work that he felt was not necessary to support the immediate demands of the new project. As he commented: "at the end of the day the accountability lies with the senior management".

The Clients... Well, actually, we don't know much about them. No one asked. The Memorial had very active marketing and audience evaluation sections, as well as an events section that would be likely to use the vehicles for open days and other special activities but, for some reason, these sections do not appear to have been involved in the development of the proposal. This was possibly because all the parties involved shared the perception that there were a lot of clients "out there" with events just waiting to be targeted, and that therefore it was unnecessary to spend time doing market research. Many private organisations own collections of military and other historic vehicles which are run at public events, and the Director, the ADNC at the time, the Curator and several members of the workshop staff had experience as private owners and operators of historic vehicles which exposed them to a range of events that they may have seen as potential candidates for Memorial vehicle displays. The decision to spend money on increasing the variety of periods represented by operational vehicles certainly suggests a strategic intention to make the Memorial's operating fleet attractive to a wider range of events, although it is

also clear that the Mobile Vehicles project was initially expected to cater predominantly to local clients – heritage institutions similar to the Memorial – with the vehicles driving only relatively short distances. In a letter exploring the legalities of the registration and running of historic vehicles, the Curator wrote:

It is envisaged that the vehicles will travel less than 200kms each year, with the 1959 Land Rover with recoilless rifle being the most regularly used vehicle at perhaps 5 times per year. The vehicles would most commonly be driven from the Memorial's Treloar Centre at Mitchell [in Canberra] to either the Memorial [display building] at Campbell or other national cultural institution [sic] in Canberra...¹³

Without further market research, however, these estimates of potential events were optimistic, as requests from local clients for Memorial vehicles for their events had, on average, only occurred once or twice a year.

How things played out

Misunderstandings

Work began on the Mobile Vehicles project in 2001, and one of the first tasks was to draft a policy to establish the procedures to be observed in managing the program. This included the Memorial's statutory obligations for complying with historic licensing conditions, the roles and responsibilities of staff involved in the project, the sequence of steps to be observed by staff organising vehicle deployments, and the criteria by which vehicles would be judged appropriate for use in the project. This document went through a number of permutations before a final version emerged in November 2005, and, while no version of the document explicitly states the aims of the project, the different versions provide a glimpse of changing ideas about exactly what the project did or did not include. For instance, the fifteen vehicles identified in the 2001 list of vehicles for the project¹⁴ were all expected to take part in operational displays, but the twenty-five vehicles identified in the earliest version of the policy document in 2002 included a number of vehicles that were to be maintained for other reasons.

Others [sic] mobile historic vehicles are unregistered. They are maintained...for the purposes of movement with the storage

¹³ AWM file 01/2354, p. 1, Letter to John Brosolo, Department of Urban Services, 20 December, 2000. In due course the Memorial was granted the status of a Historic Vehicles Club, to allow it to operate vehicles on public roads under restricted licence conditions.

¹⁴ AWM file 01/2354, n.p. "Australian War Memorial: Vehicles for Mobile Display", 27 March 2001.

area, ... and displays at other venues that do not include mobile demonstration.¹⁵

The conservation treatment of a vehicle is, of course, very use-specific – particularly if maintenance must be minimised to keep costs down – and the practical consequences of different categories of vehicle usage quickly became apparent. For instance, vehicles that were not going to be registered to drive on public roads did not need the addition of modern safety features such as indicator lights. Unfortunately, ambiguity about the anticipated roles of some of the vehicles created different expectations in the minds of project participants about exactly what each vehicle would be required to do and exactly what treatment it needed to be given to do it.

The 2002 version of the policy also identified drivers for each of the 25 vehicles, and while they all had driving experience with military vehicles, they did not all have mechanical or engineering training. Again, treatment is use-specific: there is a significant difference between the amount of work required for a vehicle to be coaxed into starting and running by a skilled mechanic, and the amount of work required for it to be reliably started and run by a person who merely has appropriate driver training. As Col Ogilvie, a mechanic with a lifetime of experience remarked, “for a motor mechanic, what is hard to start? If it takes more than 10 minutes, yeah it's hard to start.”¹⁶ The requirement for “turn-the-key” reliability was implicit in the assumption that the vehicles for mobile display could be driven without the presence of trained mechanics, yet the requirement for extra resources to maintain vehicles in such condition was not explicitly acknowledged, either in the policy or elsewhere. In particular, keeping elderly vehicles reliable takes both regular exercise, and consistent diagnosis and repair of minor faults. This translates into regular visits to the workshop and many hours of expert attention, a process commonly referred to – and unfortunately frequently dismissed – as “maintenance”.

Maintenance is at the heart of many conflicts over large technology projects because the depth and importance of its role is often not recognised. This is partly because it does not fit the project-based management paradigm. Maintenance-based management relies on a cyclical pattern of care, a constant return to previous work for checking and adjustment and a gradual building of knowledge over long time periods and variable conditions. Project-based management relies on a stepwise, no-return pattern of achievement, a major input of resources at one point in time to effect a significant change. Success, in maintenance-based management, means achieving performance that is consistent and predictable over time, whereas success

¹⁵ AWM file 03/2320, n.p. “Draft Australian War Memorial Historic Vehicles Policy”, Draft Ver 2002:01.

¹⁶ Col Ogilvie was interviewed by Alison Wain in 2009 for a forthcoming PhD dissertation conducted at the Australian National University. Col Ogilvie has a lifetime of experience in both commercial and museum maintenance and restoration work, and currently works as an engineering consultant at the National Museum of Australia.

in project management means completing a required change and not needing to re-visit the results. Both these management techniques are useful, but they meet different needs.

Care of all heritage objects is, in reality, a cyclical maintenance process, but modern conservation services (both commercial and in-house museum laboratories) have developed a pseudo-project structure of separate phases of treatment, in which cyclical maintenance work is conceptually divided into separate jobs by activities such as the commencement and completion of conservation reports, the signing of contracts and payment of invoices, and the movement of objects into and out of laboratories or workshops. This pseudo-project structure means these activities fit well within a predominantly project based museum culture, and it works in a practical sense because most museum objects are traditionally kept in static storage and display and do not require regular intervention between major treatment phases as long as they are provided with suitable packaging and environmental conditions (in fact, many of them are physically safer left alone, though it is debatable whether this maximises their potential as heritage.) At the end of a phase of activity, further treatment is usually unnecessary unless accidental damage occurs or the object needs to be prepared for a different display. The approach does not work, though, for complex operational mechanical systems, which must be regularly exercised to circulate lubricants and surface coatings, remove corrosive internal moisture, and prevent deformation or hardening of flexible components.

Commercial restorers of historic vehicles, who are specifically concerned with complex mechanical systems, use a similar pseudo-project structure to conservation services: each time the vehicle enters a commercial workshop it does so for a specific task which has a defined beginning and end, but after this the company takes no further responsibility for the vehicle. Such companies usually fix existing faults (with either visual or mechanical restorations); they do not generally provide the ongoing exercise and pre-emptive diagnosis that prevent faults occurring in the first place and which are therefore an essential part of a vehicle being regarded as reliable. The nearest commercial companies come to pre-emptive diagnosis is if they are contracted to perform a “service” on the vehicle, at which point they may identify potential faults which are outside the scope of the service and require further work. However both the service and any jobs arising out of it are separate, pseudo-project activities, and neither constitutes an ongoing responsibility for the vehicle. Someone else must still take on the role of “looking out” for the machine, of using it often enough to know its quirks and limitations and of keeping track of when it needs further attention.

For privately owned historic vehicles, this problem is solved by the owners, for whom the whole point of having repair work done is to be able to run the vehicles, and who therefore, through their leisure activities, provide the services of monitoring, exercise and minor but essential maintenance (lubrication, tyre pressurisation etcetera) themselves. In a public collection, however, personalised interaction with, and enjoyment of, a machine is usually discouraged, both because staff should not be seen to be joy-riding at tax-payers’ expense, and also because

such interaction can encourage a sense of personal ownership of the object that is not appropriate for a public collection. This can be a particular challenge with volunteer staff, as noted by the Acting Director of the Western Australian Museum in 2008, Diana Jones:

... [their] complete and utter dedication to one object [can be amazing], but it is sometimes a little dangerous... It is the museum's [object], but really [to them] it is "theirs", and they know best and so quite bizarre things start happening... when it is an "object" [in a public collection], you can't do this sort of thing. So it can have some management implications which, unless they are nipped in the bud pretty quickly, can lead to great embarrassment.¹⁷

Exercising a vehicle in a public collection therefore has more the connotation of a task rather than a personal joy, and, because of both the proprieties mentioned above and safety and insurance requirements, must be fitted into an already full working day rather than personal leisure hours.

The importance of this point is that the management paradigm that enables an old vehicle to operate reliably is cyclical maintenance, not project-based change, but the management paradigm that is most common in the modern museum setting is project-based change, which governs high-status processes such as funding allocation and exhibition development. A key definition of success within the modern museum culture is largely that of project-based management: success means that a change has been effected and the project does not need to be revisited. Seen in these terms, once an historic object leaves the laboratory or workshop, it is considered "finished", and if it does not need to come back it is "successful". The corollary of this is that if the object does not leave the workshop it is considered "unfinished", and if it needs to come back within a short timeframe it is seen as "unsuccessful". In these project-based management terms, cyclical maintenance – which explicitly uses a practice of regularly revisiting an object to minimise the need for major changes – appears to be the very definition of failure and inefficiency. Good cyclical maintenance, in other words, is very easily mistaken for bad project management.

Different participants tried to apply both maintenance and project-based management styles to the Mobile Vehicles project. Maintenance-based management was a good match for the ongoing use of operational vehicles, and supported the secondary goals of the Workshop Manager and Staff of improving the overall, long-term condition of – and knowledge about – the vehicles. Project-based management was, however, better suited to the existing economic and exhibition development frameworks, and supported the secondary goals of the Curator and Director of achieving highly visible changes that would translate quickly into display

¹⁷ Diana Jones was interviewed by Alison Wain in 2008 for a forthcoming PhD study conducted at the Australian National University.

opportunities. Unfortunately, without recognising these differences in approach, each of the participants merely experienced frustration at the failure of other participants to meet their expectations, and these differences were consequently a major source of conflict in the project.

Different Expectations

From the start, exhibition redevelopment projects with hard deadlines drew staff time away from the Mobile Vehicles project, which had no fixed deadline and, perhaps crucially, no “Opening” to draw the media. In the restricted time available to the project, the Director and Curator wanted to see staff dedicated to the hands-on fixing of problems. They were reluctant for Workshop Staff to spend much time dismantling and inspecting objects to scope the extent of problems before starting actual repair work, as this seemed like double handling – the extent of the problems would become clearer when work began on the vehicle in earnest. They were also reluctant to have Workshop Staff attend meetings, as they felt this was a planning function that need not involve the hands-on staff. The Workshop Manager and Staff, however, found that inadequate scoping led to a constant need to revisit decisions as new information emerged during treatment, and that resolving these difficulties was best facilitated by face to face meetings between the various stakeholders. An email exchange in December 2002 between the Curator and the Workshop Manager illustrates conflicting views of this situation. The Workshop Manager commented:

...we have already experienced significant communication difficulties... I anticipate that the hour per fortnight that [a Workshop Staff member] will spend on the meeting may well save a number of hours of confusion at the workbench.

The Curator replied:

...I would question that there have been ‘significant’ communication difficulties: certainly not from my perspective, and I would also question that [a Workshop Staff member’s] attendance would save time as you suggest...I am not willing to loose [sic] more of [a Workshop Staff member’s] time in attending these meetings.

Both were trying to maximize efficiency, but while the Curator felt that it was better for decisions to be made at a management level and communicated down to the Workshop Staff, the Workshop Manager and Staff felt that face to face discussions between all the stakeholders eliminated much time-consuming “back and forth” communication by email and phone to clarify details.

The importance of detailed scoping was a dangerous thing to underestimate. As Col Ogilvie said of a recent project at the National Museum of Australia:

... it will take probably three days with two mechanics to diagnose this vehicle before we even try and turn the engine over because

we'll be taking plugs out, checking, everything so as we know we won't destroy anything if we try to start it. That's not maintenance. That's your vehicle inspection report.

With the restricted time available for the Mobile Vehicles project, contingency time (put into estimates to cover issues not identified in cursory scoping inspections), was frequently removed again as an indulgence which had no place in a lean and efficient business. This meant however, that the rough estimates of work were invariably expanded as further problems became evident, and the contingency time, which had been allocated to other jobs, had to be put back into the work program. This meant that either the vehicles stayed in the workshop for long periods waiting for staff time to become available – with, as discussed above, the negative implication that they were “unfinished” – or that they left the workshop but quickly came back again, with the equally negative implication that they were “unsuccessful”.

Even more unfortunate was the fact that more vehicles dropped off the “ready to go” list than went onto it. One reason for this was that there seemed to be very few events available for the vehicles to go to (and even fewer close enough for elderly vehicles to drive to without breaking down), which meant that the vehicles did not get the regular exercise they required. The lack of events was noted in a review of the project conducted in 2006, which commented, “The log books...[indicate] that minimal offsite usage has been made of the vehicles except for the Bushmaster IMV which...has been used on several promotional activities, including three trips to Sydney and one to Cowra.”¹⁸ The Memorial’s marketing section and the Curator both responded to the few requests for operating vehicles which did come in, but there is no record of them or anyone else in the Memorial actively promoting the availability of the vehicles. The 2006 review also notes that:

...vehicle displays at the main Memorial site are usually...on the Memorial’s “Open day” ...In recent years this has involved 20-30 [large technology] objects , the vast majority of which are transported to site...using a tilt-bed truck...The displays have been essentially static...Vehicles have rarely been started during the day, and have not been moved or “demonstrated” for the public. This pattern of usage derives no added value from vehicles being mobile and registered.

Both internal (Memorial) and external clients seemed relatively unconcerned about either the conflict or period represented by a vehicle, since the same vehicle (the Bushmaster IMV, see Fig. 2) went to most events and was chosen “because of its ‘drivability’ and high degree of audience impact”, not because of its relevance to a particular conflict. This means that the expansion of the operating vehicle fleet to

¹⁸ The logbook for the Bushmaster IMV, checked on 03.09.2010, shows that the vehicle only attended one other event before 2006: a Subaru Rally at Sutton, near Canberra. Since 2006, as will be discussed later, the vehicle has attended only one further event – a Memorial Open Day.

represent a larger range of periods, a key objective in the development of the 2001 list of vehicles for the project, had no perceived value for clients. In fact, the audience impact of the Bushmaster IMV was due to its currency rather than its type or period per se, as it was a new type of vehicle and had been deployed in recent conflicts, but both these attractions were in danger, as the review noted, of wearing thin as their novelty waned. The only regular (annual) client for the vehicles, the Memorial's Events Team, were also unconcerned about whether the vehicles were operational, as they did not require, or perhaps even want, this extra complication in their Open Day events.

Fig. 2 The Bushmaster IMV. As a relatively new vehicle, the Bushmaster had both novelty and currency value, and was able to drive long distances to promotional events without breaking down. Reproduced with permission from the Australian War Memorial.

Without suitable events to provide exercise for them, the vehicles needed staff to take them on maintenance runs, and as staff rarely had time to do this the lack of exercise caused new faults to develop. In addition, most of the vehicles were at the point in their lives where, due to age, years of service use, and periods of post-service neglect, so many parts were on the cusp of failure that, paradoxically, both exercising and not exercising them could lead to further defects. Each one needed an extensive overhaul followed by regular monitoring and adjustment to become once more reasonably reliable, but again, this implied that after its overhaul each supposedly "finished" vehicle would be back in the workshop repeatedly, a scenario which did not fit the project management model and was not regarded as an indicator of success.

It is perhaps surprising that the Curator particularly, with his personal experience of maintaining a private operational collection, should have felt so frustrated by the regular recurrence of faults in the vehicles, but interviews with a number of producers of large technology heritage displays (museum professionals, volunteers and private owners), have indicated that people often underestimate time spent maintaining operational large technology objects. As an example, Richard Garcia, large technology conservator at the Western Australian Museum, stated that the maintenance required to keep one of the museum's cars in operating condition for events was only a minor service twice a year. Further questioning revealed however, that the minor service actually included movement of the vehicle to and from a workshop, and starting the engine and checking safety equipment; that display preparation required a further detailed check, engine start and fixing of any problems; that operation at an event commonly identified new problems which would then have to be fixed; and that post display the vehicle had to be cleaned before it was put away. His initial response that maintenance was minimal was at odds with the considerable investment of time and money that emerged as he thought more explicitly about the different process involved.¹⁹

Much of the frustration felt by both the Director and the Curator, though, was due to their feeling that the Workshop Staff were spending a lot of time on unnecessary tasks, particularly documentation. This is where the secondary goals of different players became most evident as thorough documentation of the processes of examination and treatment, and the translation of this information into permanent archival forms, was seen as vital by the Workshop Manager and Staff, but as largely irrelevant by the Director and Curator. As discussed in the first section of this paper, the Workshop Manager and Staff felt that information on the current condition of the objects could only be collected in the present, but that once it was collected it would form an immense resource for the future, providing opportunities for research and display as well as guidance for treatment and troubleshooting which would reduce future maintenance times. They understood that a number of the vehicles had little provenance and had been collected as type examples (several specifically for the purpose of operational display), but they were also aware that, due to the Curator's expertise, the "type" vehicles were very good examples of their kind, and represented substantial monetary investments by the Memorial. As such, they knew these vehicles were likely to remain in the collection in the long term, probably long beyond their use in the Mobile Vehicles project. The Director and Curator felt, however, and with equal validity, that such documentation had little impact on the success of the existing Mobile Vehicles project, and in fact, by taking up precious time, may well have been hampering it. A terse directive from 2005: "time spent on documentation must be kept under control with as many efficiencies built in as possible", is a brief reminder of the heated debates that surrounded this topic.²⁰

¹⁹ Richard Garcia was interviewed by Alison Wain in 2008 for a forthcoming PhD dissertation conducted at the Australian National University.

²⁰ AWM file 08/2160, n.p., "Major Conservation Project Steering Group Meeting", 24 February 2005.

Documentation of the condition and treatment of objects was, however, accepted conservation procedure for all other types of collection objects within the Memorial, so why was it such a bone of contention for large technology objects? The answer was threefold. Firstly, there was the issue of size: large technological objects are assemblies of myriad smaller objects, each one of which can take as much time to examine and document as a whole item in another collection. Thus, the level of documentation that would be required for a small object such as a sword – perhaps two paragraphs of writing and two photographs – became, for a vehicle, several pages of text and fifty photographs. Secondly, there was the issue of background and expectations: people who were employed as mechanics were not expected to produce much written documentation and were not provided with the administrative facilities that were standard in the rest of the institution. From 1996-2005 the only areas for documentation work in the Conservation Workshop of the Memorial were odd corners filled with scavenged office furniture, while computer access was mostly restricted to shared machines in a different part of the building.

A third issue was that conservation documentation within the Memorial was in a transition phase, moving from hardcopy records stored in envelopes to digital notes and images stored in a single database that integrated all collection information, from catalogue and conservation details to location and exhibition history. The move to the new database occurred in 2000, but the conservation module of the database was still in a very early stage of development. Crucially for large technology objects, methods had to be invented to allow the database to handle successive phases of treatment, separate movement and treatment of subdivided sections of the same object, uploading, captioning and storage of large batches of images and connecting images to specific phases of treatment. The software went through many trial stages, was often unavailable for use, and the early versions had a frustrating tendency to lose data and links.

All these factors made documentation an uphill process for the Workshop Staff. That they persevered with it is due both to their commitment to its importance, and to nagging from the Workshop Manager. The difficulties did, however, mean that reports and photographs were often left to accumulate until they formed large and time-consuming backlogs. This did not recommend them to the Director and Curator, who regarded the documentation as only marginally necessary in the first place.

With so few events, vehicles dropping off the “ready-to-go” list, and the Workshop Manager and Staff asking for more time than the Director and Curator wanted to allocate, the project was unraveling fast. Emotions were running high, and attitudes were becoming polarized. There are at least three ways such high-pressure systems can go: denial that the problem exists, a big fight, or a radical and honest reassessment of the project. It is a testament to the professionalism of all the Memorial’s staff that they took the last, and the most challenging and disciplined, of these paths.

Regaining control

As the participants began to take action to regain control over the project, their different aims and personalities made it difficult for them work together to find a solution. Each of them therefore began to address the problem in ways that reflected their secondary goals, roles within the organisation, background experiences and personal problem-solving methods.

The Workshop Manager drew on her experience in managing and using information, realizing that the data needed to monitor and assess the project was both scattered and non-standardised. Time sheets were handwritten and kept in the Workshop, and only really accessible to Workshop staff. Costs were noted in digital documents in the Collection Services shared drive, which was not readily accessed by the Director or Curator. Neither time nor costs for the project could be tracked in the Memorial's computerized accounting system, because the system could not accommodate separate codes for such sub-projects, or allow data input by staff in non-managerial positions. Scoping and treatment documents were theoretically held in the Conservation module of the Collection Database, which was unfamiliar to the Director and Curator. This module was also very difficult to use, with the result that in practice these documents were more often held on the personal drives of Workshop Staff.

The scope of the project was also open to considerable interpretation. The Mobile Vehicles Policy (in its 2002 version) said of vehicle availability:

Where a Mobile Historic Vehicle becomes defective and would require *substantial* work to reinstate it to mobile or roadworthy standard, Workshop personnel should consult with the Mobile Historic Vehicles Registrar and the Head of Collection Services before undertaking such work. [Italics in the original.]

Different perceptions of the meaning of "substantial work" meant that, in practice, Workshop Staff felt required to request permission of senior staff to undertake almost any task on the vehicles, which was a time consuming process and also exacerbated senior staff members' perceptions that there were an exceptional number of defects occurring on the vehicles. In 2004-2005 the Workshop Manager began to look for ways to regularize terms, formats and processes and to bring different types of data together.

Responding to this, Andrew Schroeder of the Workshop Staff drew on his experience in the commercial vehicle maintenance industry to find solutions that might be adapted for use in a heritage context. In particular, he began to explore the potential of fleet management software to provided a standardized, centralised database of the faults on the vehicles, the actions taken and the time and cost involved. The ADNC ultimately decided that such software would be an unnecessary complication

and expense,²¹ but the research did help Andrew develop ideas about how to gather and present maintenance time and cost data in a succinct and standard manner.

Andrew also drew on both his mechanical and conservation science training to explore the possibility of using vapour phase inhibitors (VPIs) to prevent corrosion and reduce the amount of exercise needed by the operational vehicles, while still allowing them to be driven at short notice. He initially envisaged that the time no longer required for exercise would be reallocated to intensive overhauls and fixing problems, but in fact his research quickly led to the more radical idea of completely “mothballing” the internal systems of rarely used vehicles. Mothballed vehicles would no longer be ready to drive at short notice, but this had proved unnecessary anyway for most of the vehicles, and mothballing – if done appropriately – could be reversed if needs changed in the future.

The Curator drew on his experience and network as a private collector, through which he had become familiar with working with commercial companies which specialised in the restoration of old vehicles. He had previously initiated external contract work on Memorial vehicles, in particular for a group of motorcycles, and felt that this approach provided a more efficient, “cut and dried” result – an agreed result in an agreed time frame for an agreed price. He pressed for more vehicles to be sent out for contract restoration, especially those which had been acquired as type examples and which had little significant provenance. He also pressed for mechanics with commercial rather than conservation backgrounds to be employed in the Conservation Workshop, believing that they would focus on the tasks he felt were most critical – such as making the vehicles look good and making them work – rather than the tasks he felt were less critical, such as documenting historical evidence and treatment processes, and undertaking work that would reduce maintenance times in the future but make little difference in the present.

The Director drew on his high-level experience of management, and probably on his military training. He recognised the need to improve communication through the different levels of the Memorial hierarchy, and to develop report formats that supplied the information he needed for executive decision-making. This was not just a response to the difficulties of the Mobile Vehicles project, but a recognition that all the large technology projects were high profile, high cost, and high risk, and that successful management of these projects required a dedicated management tool. In February 2005 he initiated the Major Conservation Project Steering Group (which came to be known as CSG). As minuted at the first meeting, the key issues it needed to resolve were project management, scoping (of large technology projects) and communication.²² Members of the group were to be the ADNC, the Heads of the

²¹ AWM file 06/2350, p. 26, “Nola Anderson – fleet maintenance software”. (See handwritten notes.) 14 September 2005.

²² AWM file 08/2160, n.p., “Major Conservation Project Steering Group Meeting”, 24 February 2005.

Curatorial and Conservation sections, and other staff as required; most commonly the Workshop Manager and curators working on particular projects.²³

The CSG meeting was crucially important for resolving the challenges posed by the Mobile Vehicles project, both because it had support at the highest level of management, and because it brought together people who usually did not talk to each other, and information that was not usually combined. This helped to make hidden assumptions and secondary goals explicit, and made it essential to develop common ways of collating and assessing information. CSG was the mixing tank into which the participants could pour their various goals and separate efforts to find solutions, and from which began to flow solutions that were jointly developed, agreed and committed to. It provided a facilitator (the ADNC) and a neutral space for the discussion of issues, and written minutes for the tracking of decisions and their consequences. Once CSG was in place quite radical options began to appear, and the scope of the Mobile Vehicles project changed very fast.

At the CSG meeting of 23 November 2005 it was minuted that the Workshop Manager and the Curator would undertake a review of the Mobile Vehicle Fleet. The ADNC stipulated that the review must answer the questions “What will we use often?” and “What are the resource implications?” This prompted the Curator to comment that “a fundamental question was why we would want a mobile vehicle fleet at all”.²⁴ The enthusiasm that had accompanied the start of the project in 2000 had been replaced by a hard-headed acknowledgement that there was no business case for the project. There was no great market for operating vehicle demonstrations, and the resources required to maintain historic vehicles in operating condition were beyond what the Memorial could spare. The real question became – where should we go from here?

The Workshop Team held a brainstorming session in late November.²⁵ The investigation of VPI technology suggested that it might be feasible to divide the vehicles into two different maintenance groups – a “quick access” group to be maintained as in the original project (reliable, easily started, drivable by non-mechanics, fitted with modern safety features and registered for road use), and a “long access” group, to be mothballed using VPIs and covers. Vehicles in the long access group would not be drivable under their own power without a return-to-service programme, but systems such as doors, running gear and tyres would be periodically lubricated, moved or pressurised to keep them in sufficiently functional condition for towing, access and shape preservation.

The advantage of this idea was that it went some way to achieving the primary and secondary goals of all the participants, or at least left open the possibility of those

²³ AWM file 08/2160, n.p., “Major Conservation Project Steering Group Meeting”, 8 June 2005.

²⁴ AWM file 08/2160, n.p., “Major Conservation Project Steering Group Meeting”, 23 November 2005.

²⁵ AWM file 06/2350, pp. 66-68, “Ideas”, 21 November 2005.

goals being achieved in the future. The explicit primary goal of the project – improving the condition of selected vehicles for display – was met, as all the vehicles would be made presentable for static display, and a small group of them would be made reliable for operational display. The secondary goals of the Workshop Team – improving the condition and knowledge of the vehicles and their functional systems – would be partially met through the examination, documentation and basic repairs done to facilitate mothballing, and the ongoing corrosion protection provided by the VPIs, with the option of taking that work further in the future as funds, time and exhibition priorities allowed. The secondary goals of the Curator and Director – improving the ability of the collection to represent the development and use of vehicles by Australians in conflict, and minimising maintenance costs – would be partially met through the acquisition of new collection items, cosmetic work on existing items, and the reduction of maintenance requirements through the use of VPIs. While all the participants had been hoping for more, all of them were able to see some progress towards their collective and individual goals.

Andrew's exploration of fleet management documentation enabled him to reduce the perceived complexity and cyclical nature of workshop maintenance tasks to a single set of time and labour costs for each vehicle that had been treated during the 2005 calendar year. This made clear which vehicles were hardest to maintain in operational condition, and conversely, which vehicles were most cost-effective to maintain in operational condition. This presentation resonated immediately with the Curator, who was able to overlay an interpretive filter to decide which of the easy-to-maintain vehicles would have most audience impact at promotional displays.

On 24 January 2006 the Curator presented a minute to the ADNC which included a brief history of the Mobile Vehicle project, the past and projected maintenance costings from the Workshop Manager and Staff, and the proposal to separate the vehicle collection into a larger, mothballed, static display group, and a smaller operational display group.²⁶ After further discussion the minute was rewritten to include an evaluation of the usage of vehicles for operation and static display over the period of the Mobile Vehicle project, and to further distill the maintenance cost information. The final document²⁷ was presented on 10 February 2006 to the Memorial's Corporate Management Group (CMG), a group that included the Director and all three Assistant Directors of the Memorial, and that represented co-ordinated consideration and decision-making at the Memorial's highest executive level. CMG approved the proposal to separate the vehicles into static and operational display groups, the suggestion of regularly reviewing the benefits of maintaining selected vehicles in operational condition, and the recommendation that "Consideration be given to using historic vehicle associations on occasions when

²⁶ AWM file 01/2354, n.p. "Minute to Nola Anderson ADNC – Review of Mobile Vehicles." 24 January 2006. See note 4.

²⁷ AWM file 07/3205, pp. 15-19, "CMG paper: Proposal to Rationalise Maintenance on Vehicles Used for Public Program Displays", presented to CMG on 10 February 2006.

a mobile fleet is required.”²⁸ CMG also identified which vehicles were to be prioritised for static and operational display preparation, and added a Land Rover to the Curator’s recommendation of the Bushmaster IMV as the only vehicles to be maintained in operational condition.²⁹

Outcomes

These decisions were acted upon in short order. In March 2006, barely four months since the idea of a review of the project had first been raised, a note was sent to the Director confirming the changed work plans for the vehicles.³⁰ Ten vehicles were to have their operational systems mothballed by Memorial Workshop staff:

... vehicles will be drained, cleaned and have all enclosed spaces/components inhibited. Batteries will be removed, brakes backed off and the vehicles prepared for towing in their mothballed condition (for easy movement)...

Two vehicles were to be sent to external contractors for restoration as static display vehicles: this would involve corrosion stabilisation and cosmetic restoration of visible areas, but no attempt to return the vehicles to self-powered operation. The Bushmaster IMV and a Land Rover, as mentioned above, were to be maintained in fully operational, road registered condition, at an estimated cost of \$1600/144 hours for the Bushmaster and \$300/100 hours for the Land Rover.³¹

In many ways the vehicle collection had come full circle, though the Mobile Vehicles project had resulted in some changes to the way resources were allocated that arguably improved maintenance coverage of the vehicle collection and went further toward achieving Memorial goals:

- as before there was a long-term maintenance program, but the focus of this had changed from using self-powered operation to maintain movement and corrosion protection (which in practice meant that, with limited resources, only a few vehicles could be maintained), to using hand turning and chemical passivation (which meant that a larger number of vehicles could be maintained).
- Chemical passivation, which required widely spaced, intensive treatments, but little intervention between treatments, had conveniently converted the maintenance programme to a pseudo project-based management structure,

²⁸ The Curator had contacts with a number of historic vehicle associations, and although there were transport and accommodation costs associated with their use, these costs were lower for the Memorial than maintaining a permanent operating vehicle fleet of its own.

²⁹ AWM file 07/3205, pp. 20-21, “Email from Curator (Mike Cecil) to Workshop manager (Alison Wain). Subject: Directors [sic] vehicle list.” 23 February, 2006.

³⁰ Collection Services Section digital archive, “Minute to CMG: Large technology conservation program for the next five years”, 14 March 2006.

³¹ The costs are detailed in the “Current and projected Fleet Maintenance” section of the review document presented to CMG on 10 February 2006. AWM file 07/3205, pp. 15-19.

which brought it into line with other conservation and management processes in the Memorial;

- once again there were two operational vehicles road registered for use at promotional events, but the vehicles maintained for this purpose were felt to be more appropriate to a promotional and representative role than those previously used;
- as before, certain vehicles were selected to be visually restored for static display, but these projects were to be done externally, to take advantage of the perceived efficiency of commercial restoration firms.

In 2010, four years on from the review, four further observations can be made.

Firstly, the two operational display vehicles have been used for only one promotional event each in the four years, and there are now thoughts of mothballing even these vehicles.

Secondly, while Andrew had hoped that VPIs could reduce the servicing requirements of operational vehicles, the mothballing program has actually replaced operational maintenance almost entirely, and most vehicles are once more preserved as static objects.

Thirdly, the use of external contractors was not a panacea, mostly because the anticipated efficiencies turned out not to be applicable to a heritage context. Efficiencies can be delivered through bulk processing of similar items, but this does not apply to a heritage collection in which almost every vehicle is a different type or model, and where the vehicles' different life histories mean that they have highly idiosyncratic needs. Costs can be reduced by using quicker and cheaper work methods, but the results do not necessarily meet the visual, safety or useability standards required of objects in a national heritage collection. And when contractors are uncertain of potential problems, or are asked to meet high standards, they may either raise their quotes to cover the additional labour and materials, or progressively advise the owner of new work not covered in the original quote. The Conservation Manager flagged problems as early as 2005:

It should be noted that sending a vehicle out as a complete package for contract work does not provide a fixed cost commitment, as the work program invariably requires revision as the vehicle is dismantled and its internal condition becomes more apparent.³²

³² Collection Services Section digital archive, "Minute to CMG: Large technology conservation program for the next five years", 14 March 2006.

In February 2007 it was minuted that the restoration of the Diamond T truck was “progressing slowly - wheels more difficult to treat than contractor anticipated,”³³ and in August 2009 that “Restoration of the Studebaker and Chevrolet cars by VMG is approximately 2 weeks behind schedule.” In August 2009 it was also minuted that “The quote for the Wiles Cooker was \$59,642.00. CSG agreed that the restoration would be undertaken in-house by conservation staff for a fraction of the cost.”³⁴ Good restoration work on historic vehicles takes time, money and care, whether it is done by in-house staff or external contractors.

Fourthly, the most successful change to come out of the Mobile Vehicles project was probably the CSG forum, which in 2010 is still going strong. Its success confirms the need for strong links from senior management right through to the workshop floor, to enable organisations to manage the stresses imposed by the high costs and high stakes of large technology heritage.

What did we learn?

The difficulties faced during the Mobile Vehicles project led to innovation and change in several areas of practices: the way vehicles were maintained, the way work on the vehicles was managed, and the way information and decisions about the vehicles was shared between different sections and levels of Memorial staff. No one of these changes was solely responsible for resolving the conflicts and regaining control over the project, but together they were enough to finally draw the frayed strands of the project into an integrated whole, albeit with less ambitious aims than at the start of the venture. When we began writing this paper, it was these practical insights that we wanted to share.

As we wrote, though, we began to realise that, while these procedural innovations were very useful, two of the most significant lessons from the project related to broader understandings of what it means, and what it takes, to present successful and sustainable operational technology heritage displays. These were lessons about the culture, orientation and commitment of an organisation as a whole, and they may go some way to explaining why the static and operational display of heritage machines are so rarely successfully integrated within a single site or organisation.

The first of these lessons was that the display of large operational machines requires a distinctively different set of resources to that required for the display of static objects. Traditional museums, such as the Memorial, have spent decades investing in the collection objects, the buildings, the equipment, the procedures and the staff to produce the most effective static displays. They have not invested the same amount of time, money or thought into building up similar resources for operational displays. It is not immediately obvious that these two display methods are so different in their requirements, but the Mobile Vehicles project helped to demonstrate that they are,

³³ Collection Services Section digital archive, “Major Conservation Project Steering Group Meeting”, 16 February 2007.

³⁴ Collection Services Section digital archive, “Major Conservation Project Steering Group Meeting”, 13 August 2009.

and that the level of commitment and resources required to change from one to the other, or to integrate the two, is very high. The participants in the Mobile Vehicles project hoped to establish a successful operational display programme by merely adding a few resources to an existing maintenance programme, but without the addition of substantial organisational change, and a major investment in new skills, facilities and administrative support, the weight of the institutional culture rolled over the project and reinstated the status quo. With hindsight it is apparent that, given the level of resources and the culture of the organisation, the original maintenance programme was actually a fairly efficient and sustainable balance between inputs and outcomes.

The second of these lessons is that good audience evaluation and marketing are as crucial to the success of large technology displays as they are to any other exhibitions. It is not enough just to have a big impressive object that works – the object must also have a recognisable identity in the minds of visitors, and be something that they want to visit and revisit.³⁵ This requires audience evaluation to find out what would make the object engaging and accessible for them, and marketing to ensure that they know about it and find it attractive. Again, this is where organisations that focus predominantly on operational displays are different to those that are focussed on static display. Organisations such as Puffing Billy foreground their operational displays in their publicity, whereas museums whose traditional business is static displays tend to feature these most prominently in their advertising, framing operating technology displays as “extra” attractions rather than as essential parts of the visitor experience. Visitors are likely, however, to plan their visit around what they perceive as the core attractions of the museum, and may remain unaware, or have no time and energy left, for things that seem to be optional extras. Low interest from visitors, of course (or in the case of the Memorial’s Mobile Vehicles project, event clients), quickly leads an organisation to see a display as unsuccessful and to either withdraw resources or remove the display altogether, which is exactly what happened to the operational display of vehicles at the Memorial.

It is good to improve technical and management practices, and to align them more precisely to organisational needs. Such improvements have the potential to save resources, reduce stressful conflicts for staff and improve outcomes for visitors. They will have little long term impact, however, unless steps are also taken to understand and manage the powerful influence of the organisation’s wider culture and orientation.

³⁵ John H. Falk and Lynn D. Dierking, *Learning from Museums: Visitor Experiences and the Making of Meaning*, AltaMira Press, Walnut Creek, 2000, p. 179.